

Innovate the Construction of a New Model of "Three-Lead" Education and Training of "Competition Guidance, Student-Lead, and Teacher Guidance."

---- The practice of the Finance Department of Jiangsu University School of Finance and Economics as an example

Author's Details:

Guoping Ding, Wenshu Chen, Shichen Yuan

Jiangsu University, School of Finance and Economics, No 301, Xuefu Road, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu, China, 212013, Corresponding Author: Guoping Ding, Email: 1000003062@ujs.edu.cn.

Abstract:

This article takes the teaching practice of competition education carried out by the Finance Department of Jiangsu University School of Finance and Economics as an example. It introduces the various national, provincial and municipal competitions that the Finance Department has guided students to participate in recent years. It is believed that the new training model of "competition guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance, "which is the "three guidance" education, is not only conducive to improving the comprehensive quality of students and the teaching level of teachers but also expanding the visibility of schools and majors, and achieve a win-win situation among students, teachers, and schools. In the future, schools should explore the development of multi-disciplinary integration, actively encourage students to participate in comprehensive competitions, and carry out cross-disciplinary and cross-field cooperation to cultivate compound talents.

Keywords: *competition education; competition guidance; student-led; teacher guidance; teaching mode*

1. The origin of the competition education

The overseas university student science and technology competition originated earlier, and the organization scale is large, and the level is high. As early as 1950, Spain and Portugal initiated and founded the World Skills Organization. In 1951, competitions began to be held. Some European countries participated earlier and formed a relatively complete competition system in competition categories, competition participation, competition organization, competition recognition, and reward policies. Take the international college student programming competition as an example. In the past ten years, the competition has developed and gained a certain reputation. Some of the world-renowned information companies, such as Apple, Microsoft, and IBM, have served as competition sponsors, attracting many high-level and high-level students to participate.

China's competitive education's rise and development mainly rely on policy support, national attention, and positive responses from universities. China established the China Higher Education Association in 1983, responsible for academic exchanges, professional training, exhibitions, and other tasks. In 2008, China initiated the compilation of the "National Medium and Long-term Education Reform and Development Plan (2010-2020)" and proposed to deepen higher education reform, focus on the quality of talent training, and promote the close integration of technological innovation, academic development, and talent training in universities. In 2017, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council issued the "Medium and Long-term Youth Development Plan (2016-2025)", which pointed out that it is necessary to successfully organize entrepreneurial brand activities such as the Youth Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competition to improve the quality of young innovative talent training. In order to implement the spirit of the document, the Ministry of Science and Technology, the Ministry of Education, and the Central Committee of the Youth League have successively launched various national discipline competitions. These competitions have also become the main front for reform and innovation education in colleges and

universities, playing an important role in education, teaching, and cultivation of innovative talents.

At present, the academic circles have richer researches on competition education, mainly focusing on the connotation of competition education, university practice, and the positive impact of competition education on students, teachers, and schools. Huang Lijuan (2020) believes that competition education refers to stimulating students' interest in learning, enthusiasm, and initiative through competition, strengthening students' professional quality, and improving students' professional skills and professional practice ability. Zhang Wencui (2019) uses Guangdong University of Foreign Studies as an example to explore the "three, four, four, one" education model of promoting learning through competition. It is believed that the promotion of learning by competition refers to the combination of professional knowledge and skills in teaching activities and the organization of relevant competitions to better conduct teaching activities. Walan et al. (2018) conducted interviews with teachers and principals of 17 universities in Sweden to analyze students' status quo and reasons for participating in science and technology competitions. The study found that students' participation in science and technology competitions is conducive to improving students' comprehensive quality. Therefore, schools should incorporate various valuable competitions into higher education, teachers should pay attention to the connection between competitions and course learning when teaching, and university principals should play the role of organizing publicity competitions and providing social support. Anonymous (2011) took university student science and technology competition as the research object and analyzed the effectiveness of practical teaching in college education. It is believed that practical teaching, as the fusion point of theory and practice, knowledge and ability, creates an open platform for school innovation education, expands the scope of school-enterprise cooperation, actively promotes students to carry out innovative, practical activities, and improves students' comprehensive quality. Scholars at home and abroad have carried out extensive research on event education, which provides a useful reference and reference for the implementation of the implementation path and teaching plan of event education.

2. Implementation plan for competition education

(1) Competition guidance: Promoting learning and teaching through competition

The practical teaching mode of "promoting teaching and learning by competition" is the product of the combination of the teaching needs of colleges and universities and the needs of social practice. It is characteristic teaching that effectively combines teaching, practice, and innovation. Specifically, "promoting learning by competition" is a mode that uses competition to mobilize students' enthusiasm for learning, expand the breadth and depth of students' professional learning, effectively improve the quality of students' learning, enhance students' overall quality, and cultivate students' good independent learning ability. "Promoting teaching with competition" refers to college teachers who organize and guide students to participate in competitions in the daily teaching process to find the shortcomings of their own classroom theory teaching and professional practical operation ability and to test their teaching ability and teaching quality. It is a model for improving the problems that arise, continuously improving the theoretical teaching knowledge system and teaching plan, promoting teaching reform and practice, and gradually improving the teaching level of teachers. Among them, "competition" is the means, and promotion of "learning" and "teaching" is the goal.

Competition education uses competition as a carrier to improve the comprehensive quality of students and the teaching level of teachers. Therefore, the development of high-quality competitions should be the premise. First of all, at the national level: On the one hand, it is necessary to set reasonable competition conditions and enrich the competition content. The education department should do a good job in the overall

planning, and set the competition requirements according to the different development requirements of different disciplines. It should be scientifically and rationally opened and enrich the content of the competition. On the other hand, it is necessary to strengthen the management of competition organizations at all levels and promote its standardization. It is best to be fixed in the form of law to provide a reliable legal basis for launching and promoting various competitions and participating in international competitions so that the competition can be run in an orderly manner. Secondly, at the social level: On the one hand, government agencies and local societies should actively host various events, increase funding and support for talent training, and build a platform for the competition. On the other hand, enterprises and R&D platforms should actively connect with the competition, recognize the value of the competition, recognize relevant certificates, and do a good job in the docking of production, education, and research; third, colleges and universities should actively respond, strengthen competition propaganda within the school, and guide students to actively participate.

Competitive education takes various competitions as the carrier, student participation as the center, and teacher guidance as to the backing. The three are closely connected to form a joint development mechanism with a coupling relationship, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The development mechanism of competition education

(2) Student-led: Actively participate in the competition

Students are the main body in the competition, so students' central position should be emphasized when the competition is implemented, and student participation should be the main focus. Therefore, for students, on the one hand, they must continue to cultivate hobbies and effectively enhance their awareness of the competition. Hobbies are the best teachers and play an important role in the cultivation of innovative, practical ability. Higher learning institutions should rely on innovative practice event platforms to vigorously cultivate students' interest in participating in innovative practice events, rationally design event procedures, streamline event registration materials, optimize event review models, scientifically set event support policies, and vigorously promote innovative practices and typical character. At the same time, it is necessary to provide the greatest convenience to participating students in terms of the allocation of event instructors,

the acquisition of literature materials, the sharing of experimental equipment and equipment, and in-depth stimulation of students' enthusiasm for participating in innovative practice events. College students should establish a correct concept of innovative practice, have a firm belief and determination to struggle hard, strive to be the trendy players of the new era, and strive to be the typical figures of innovative practice. On the one hand, students must learn professional, entrepreneurial, and industrial knowledge to lay the foundation for participating in various competitions. Undergraduates should cultivate the awareness of the innovative, practical ability of "professional + entrepreneurship + industry." They should gain in-depth knowledge of the basic content, methods, risks, and other industry characteristics of practical project operation and management through familiarization with the basic knowledge of the discipline and professional field system. Through the organic combination of basic professional knowledge, practical expertise, and industry characteristic knowledge, we can achieve "professional" professional basic knowledge, "proficient" practical expertise, and "diligence" of characteristic industry knowledge. At the same time, students should actively participate in various innovative practice events of the school, internalize innovative professional knowledge, practical expertise, and characteristic industrial knowledge, gradually find gaps, improve themselves, and improve their quality.

(3) Teacher guidance: improve teaching quality

Teaching and learning are the two most important aspects of school education. There is an old saying: "Learning and then knowing the deficiencies, teaching and then knowing the difficulties. Knowing the deficiencies, then being able to reflexively, knowing the difficulties, and then strengthening oneself. Therefore, it is said: teaching and learning. Teaching is the interaction between teaching and learning. Teachers and students communicate with each other, inspire each other, and complement each other. In this process, teachers and students carry out emotional exchanges with each other so as to reach consensus, share and advance together, and achieve mutual growth and common development in teaching.

The competition's education needs to be backed by teacher guidance, learn professional knowledge from the course, introduce the content of the competition, and guide students to actively participate. First of all, schools should increase teaching facilities and improve training bases. Good practical training and teaching conditions are the keys to improving the quality of education and teaching. Attach importance to the construction and improvement of basic teaching conditions, provide practical sites, invest practical funds, allocate instructors, and improve practical experimental environmental conditions, such as purchasing databases and adding laboratories. In order to satisfy students' teaching practice and internship activities, it is possible to sign a cooperation agreement with foreign enterprises and institutions to establish a teaching practice base to provide a guarantee for the realization of the teaching model of promoting learning by competition and promoting teaching by competition. Secondly, teachers should focus on improving basic teaching skills to form a high-level teaching team. The improvement of teaching quality in colleges and universities mainly depends on the comprehensive quality of teachers. Only high-quality teachers can have high-level teaching quality. The students who compete on the field are the students, and the teachers are tested outside the field. In organizing and guiding competitions, teachers continue to promote their own teaching reforms and teaching practice research, rely on subject competitions to optimize the teaching content of courses, teach students according to their aptitude, have flexible and changeable guidance levels, and innovate teaching methods. Finally, teachers should play the basic role of classroom teaching. Classroom teaching is always the foundation of school education and an important teaching base that cannot be given up. The traditional classroom teaching content is relatively boring, the methods are outdated, and the students' enthusiasm and initiative are not high. Therefore, teachers can introduce competition items into teaching activities, fully mobilize students' initiative and enthusiasm in learning, and gradually form a

teaching system integrating teaching, learning, practicing, and competition.

3. The effectiveness of the competition education practice of the Finance Department of Jiangsu University School of Finance

(1) Introduction to the competition

The Department of Finance of the School of Finance and Economics of Jiangsu University is committed to cultivating high-quality applied professionals with strong practical and innovative capabilities. In recent years, the Department of Finance has centered on the overall requirements of "three-dimensional education," and teachers and students work together to innovate out of the "three-lead" new model of competition education of "event guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance." The college organized students to actively participate in various national, provincial, and municipal-level discipline competitions and achieved excellent results.

For example, in 2018, the 3rd National College Student Insurance Innovation and Creativity Competition hosted by the Insurance Society of China. The organizing committee of this competition received a total of 359 entries from 64 universities across the country. After preliminary review and re-evaluation, only 15 entries and one exhibition project entered the finals. Among them, the "Guardian" team of the Department of Finance stood out among many contestants, successfully entered the finals, and won the third national prize. In 2019, the "ICBC Cup" National University Student Financial Technology Innovation Competition hosted by the Industrial and Commercial Bank of China included 397 projects from 23 universities across the province. The "Nongeying" team of the Department of Finance of the School of Finance and Economics, after pre-project review, online voting, and other links, stood out among the top 13 in Jiangsu and was the only representative of the three teams in the province to conduct live demonstrations and defenses. In the end, the team won the third prize in the Central Division of the "ICBC Cup" National College Student Financial Technology Innovation Competition. In the same year, the 4th National Undergraduate Financial Innovation Competition was jointly sponsored by China Construction Bank University and Shanghai University of Finance and Economics. Twelve students from the Finance Department of the School of Finance and Economics participated in the competition under two instructors' leadership. The third prize was won in the two competitions: "Competition" and "Innovative Creative Design of New Financial Products."

(2) The effectiveness of the competition education

The Department of Finance of the School of Finance and Economics of Jiangsu University, under the guidance of the "three-lead" education training model of "competition guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance," integrates competition into curriculum teaching. Through the competition, students' enthusiasm and innovation are stimulated, competition, learning, and teaching are integrated to form a talent training model with professional characteristics, and a series of results have been achieved in schools, teachers, and students.

First, the competition is an opportunity to enhance the visibility of the school and the profession. The "three-lead" education and training model of "event guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance" encourages universities to use competitions as an opportunity to deepen school-enterprise cooperation, connect professional construction with real industry development, and promote the close connection of talent training with economic and social development, entrepreneurship and employment needs. This also makes the differentiated positioning and characteristic advantages of majors more obvious, which in turn enhances the school's running level and professional reputation.

The second is to use competition as a means to enhance students' comprehensive ability. The "three-instruction" education training model of "competition guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance" can realize the systematic cultivation of comprehensive qualities such as student innovation ability, learning ability, and teamwork ability. Colleges and universities' various professional competitions simulate a good external environment for students, which can encourage students to use theoretical knowledge in competitions while discovering their shortcomings in theoretical study and practice and actively change their learning attitudes. At the same time, students gain a sense of learning achievement through the competition, which in turn mobilizes their learning enthusiasm. In this mode, students are required to integrate fragmented professional knowledge, establish a complete knowledge system, and put them into practice so that students can be more clear about their learning direction, thereby promoting the improvement of personal, professional comprehensive ability.

The third is to use competition as the carrier to improve the professional level of teachers. Under the "three-guide" education training model of "competition guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance," teachers provide targeted guidance on teaching research and teaching practice, which is conducive to the improvement of teachers' teaching level, professionalism, and comprehensive quality, and effectively improves teaching quality. This teaching model puts forward higher requirements for teachers' professional teaching level and practical skills. In order to better solve the problems encountered by students during the competition and meet the diversified and multi-level training needs of students, teachers must learn new teaching concepts, integrate cutting-edge knowledge of the subject, and strengthen the cultivation and training of their own professional qualities and teaching capabilities. Continuously follow up the new requirements of economic and social development for professional curriculum theoretical knowledge.

4. Summary and prospect

In order to better promote the educating effect of the competition, the Finance Department of the School of Finance and Economics of Jiangsu University centered on the overall requirements of the "three holistic education" and innovated out of the "three guidance" new model of "competition guidance, student-led, and teacher guidance." Under this model, students from the School of Finance and Economics actively participated in various national, provincial, and municipal discipline competitions and achieved excellent results and practical results. It improves students' comprehensive literacy and the teaching level of teachers and expands the visibility of schools and professions, and achieves a win-win situation among students, teachers, and schools. Therefore, in future development, the school should pay attention to the competitive education of the School of Finance and Economics and promote the model to various departments. Pay attention to strengthening the communication and cooperation between the departments and carry out comprehensive competitions, requiring students from different departments and different majors to form teams to participate, and everyone performs their duties based on the knowledge they have learned, and jointly completes team works. This is not only conducive to interdisciplinary communication but also helps to cultivate teamwork and communication skills and helps to cultivate compound talents.

References:

- i. Huang Lijuan. *Relying on innovation and entrepreneurship competitions to build a training model for college students' innovation and entrepreneurship ability*[J]. *Journal of Hunan Vocational and Technical College of Posts and Telecommunications*, 2020, 19(02): 59-62.
- ii. Zhang Wencui. *Research on the Practice Education Model of "Using Competition to Promote Learning and Using Competition to Promote Innovation" in Colleges and Universities—Taking the School of Information Science and Technology of Guangdong University of Foreign Studies as an*

- example [J]. Journal of Kaifeng College of Education, 2019, 39 (05):144-145+184.*
- iii. *Xie Guang. Research on the reform of the teaching mode of computer professional courses in colleges and universities integrating competition and education[J]. Teaching and Education (Higher Education Forum), 2019(24): 86-88.*
- iv. *Walan,Mc Ewen. Teachers' and principals' reflections on student participation in a school science and technology competition[J].Research in Science & Technological Education,2018,36(4): 391-412.*
- v. *He Qingqing. A preliminary exploration of the practice teaching mode of "promoting teaching by competition, and promoting learning by competition"—Taking the course of architectural drawing and drawing as an example[J]. Journal of Tianjin University of Applied Sciences, 2018(03):82- 87.*
- vi. *Bian Mingyuan, Huang Haiyan. Reform and innovation of student science and technology competition activities integrating engineering practice education[J]. Teaching and Education (Higher Education Forum), 2018(03): 21-23.*
- vii. *Anonymous.Fecyt - Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology; Competition between females leads to infanticide in some primates[J].NewsRx Health & Science,2011.*